

Data Dictionary

1. Identification and Demographic Data

Variable Name	Description	Type	Values/Units
patient_id	Unique anonymous patient identifier	Categorical	Ex: KTR_001, KTR_002
gender	Recipient gender	Binary	0 = Female, 1 = Male
age	Age in years	Numerical	years (e.g., 54.3)
family_history_dm	Family history of diabetes	Binary	0 = No, 1 = Yes

2. Diabetes and Renal Disease History

Variable Name	Description	Type	Values/Units
dm_duration	Duration of diabetes in years	Numerical	years (e.g., 10.5)
primary_kidney_disease	Primary kidney disease	Categorical	1 = Diabetic Kidney Disease (DKD), 2 = Glomerular Disease, 3 = Polycystic Disease, 4 = Tubulointerstitial Disease, 5 = Other, 6 = Unknown
renal_replacement_therapy	Pre-transplant renal replacement therapy	Categorical	1 = Hemodialysis, 2 = Peritoneal Dialysis, 3 = None

3. Transplantation Information

Variable Name	Description	Type	Values/Units
time_since_kt	Time from transplantation to study inclusion (years)	Numerical	years (e.g., 2.5)
deceased_donor	Deceased donor	Binary	0 = No, 1 = Yes
graft_number	Graft number	Categorical	1 = First, 2 = Second, 3 = More than two

4. Serologies and Immunosuppression

Variable Name	Description	Type	Values/Units
hepatitis_c	Positive hepatitis C serology	Binary	0 = Negative, 1 = Positive
cmv_positive	Positive CMV serology	Binary	0 = Negative, 1 = Positive
immunosuppression	Type of immunosuppression	Categorical	1 = Prednisone (PDN), 2 = Mycophenolate Mofetil (MMF), 3 = Azathioprine (AZA), 4 = Tacrolimus (TAC), 5 = Cyclosporine (CsA), 6 = mTOR Inhibitors (mTORi)

5. Outcome Variables

Variable Name	Description	Type	Values/Units
Metabolic			
hba1c	Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c)	Numerical	% (e.g., 7.5)
fbg	Fasting blood glucose (FPG)	Numerical	mg/dL
ldl_cholesterol	LDL cholesterol	Numerical	mg/dL
systolic_bp	Systolic blood pressure	Numerical	mmHg
body_weight	Body weight	Numerical	kg
bmi	Body Mass Index (BMI)	Numerical	kg/m ²
Graft Function			
egfr	Estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR)	Numerical	mL/min/1.73m ²
serum_creatinine	Serum creatinine	Numerical	mg/dL
Survival			
graft_survival	Graft survival	Binary	0 = Loss, 1 = Functioning
patient_survival	Patient survival	Binary	0 = Death, 1 = Alive
Complications			
mace	Major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE)	Binary	0 = No, 1 = Yes
microvascular_events	Microvascular complications (retinopathy, neuropathy, nephropathy)	Binary	0 = No, 1 = Yes

6. Medications

Variable Name	Description	Type	Values/Units
antidiabetic_use	Use of antidiabetic medications	Binary	0 = No, 1 = Yes
lipid_lowering_use	Use of lipid-lowering medications	Binary	0 = No, 1 = Yes
antihypertensive_use	Use of antihypertensive medications	Binary	0 = No, 1 = Yes
